

A Comparative Study of Dexmedetomidine versus Midazolam with Fentanyl for Monitored Anaesthesia Care in Tympanoplasty under Local Anaesthesia

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Abstract

Background and Aims: Monitored anaesthesia care is a process in which several medicines are used to administer local anaesthesia and sedation. This comparative study was done to determine the safety and efficacy of Dexmedetomidine and midazolam with fentanyl for tympanoplasty under MAC.

Methods: Sixty patients between the ages of 18 and 60 years who were scheduled for tympanoplasty under MAC were randomly divided into two groups. Group D (n = 30) patients were administered intravenous (IV) dexmedetomidine 1 mcg/kg as a bolus followed by 0.2 ml/kg/h normal saline infusion. Patients in Group MF (n =30) received intravenous administration of midazolam 0.05 mg/kg + fentanyl 1.5 mcg/kg as a bolus, followed by 0.2 ml/kg/h normal saline infusion. Intraoperatively, the heart rate (HR), mean arterial pressure (MAP), amount of sedation, and degree of analgesia were evaluated. Postoperatively, Pulse Rate (PR) and Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) were evaluated. The data were analyzed using an unpaired t-test.

Result: Dexmedetomidine produced significant decrease in heart rate and mean arterial pressure, improved sedation and analgesia during surgery, and a reduced need for rescue sedative and analgesic dosages.

Conclusion: Dexmedetomidine is superior to midazolam and fentanyl for sedation and analgesia during tympanoplasty surgery under supervised anaesthetic care because it results in a better hemodynamic profile, sedation, and analgesia.

Keyword: Tympanoplasty, Local Anaesthesia, Sedation, Dexmedetomidine, Midazolam with Fentanyl.

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Introduction

Reconstruction of a perforated tympanic membrane, with or without ossiculoplasty, constitutes tympanoplasty. [1] Local anaesthesia with sedation under monitored anaesthesia care (MAC) or general anaesthesia is typically used. [2-4]. Local anaesthetic combined with intravenous sedation has various advantages, including decreased bleeding, cost-effectiveness, postoperative analgesia, speedier patient movement, and the possibility to test hearing during surgery.[5]

Monitored anaesthesia care (MAC) often entails the administration of local anaesthesia in conjunction with intravenous (IV) sedatives, anxiolytic, and/or analgesic medications; this is a common practise throughout many ENT surgical procedures. [6]

The most prevalent discomforts experienced by MESs patients under LA were noise during surgery, anxiety, dizziness, backache, claustrophobia, and ear ache.[7] To alleviate these discomforts, proper sedation is required.[8] In MAC, sedative medications such as benzodiazepines, opioids, propofol, and 2-agonist are utilised. [9]

Due to its anxiolysis, sedation, and anterograde amnesia, midazolam is appropriate for treatment with LA. [8] Even though it has a rapid onset, the extended half-life of repeated administrations can result in persistent drowsiness. [10] Fentanyl was introduced as an analgesic because midazolam has a sedative effect but no analgesic property. However, no medication is totally free of side effects. Propofol causes cardio-respiratory depression, whereas midazolam and fentanyl increase the risk for hypoxemia and apnea [11,12]. Dexmedetomidine, a selective alpha-2 adreno-receptor agonist, induces forgetfulness, drowsiness, potentiates opioid

analgesia, and induces sympatholysis in addition to other effects.[13].

The purpose of this study was to evaluate and compare the efficacy of Dexmedetomidine and midazolam with fentanyl in terms of sedation, analgesic, and hemodynamic stability in patients having tympanoplasty under local anaesthesia with monitored anaesthetic care.

Materials and Methods

From December 2021 to November 2022, this was a prospective, randomised controlled, and double blind study conducted in the department of Anaesthesiology at Panimalar medical college hospital & research centre, Chennai. Prior to beginning the study, the institutional ethics committee approved it. 60 patients of either sex aged 18 to 60 years with ASA grade 1-2 posted for tympanoplasty under LA and sedation were included, and all subjects provided written informed consent. Patients with known sensitivity to the local anaesthetic medication lignocaine, as well as those who were pregnant or lactating, were excluded from the trial.

Premedication with glycopyrrolate 0.2mg and ondansetron 4mg was given intravenously 30 minutes before operation. Each patient received two 50-ml syringes labelled loading and maintenance. A computer-generated randomization procedure was used to divide the patients into two equal groups: Group D (dexmedetomidine) and Group MF (Midazolam Fentanyl). In their respective loading dose syringes diluted up to 30 ml of normal saline, Group D patients received dexmedetomidine 1 mcg/kg and Group MF patients received midazolam 0.03 mg/kg plus fentanyl 1 g/kg. Group D received 1 mcg/ml dexmedetomidine diluted to 50 ml in normal saline, whereas Group MF received normal

saline filled to 50 ml in their maintenance syringes. Loading dose infusions were delivered intravenously over 10 minutes in both groups, followed by maintenance infusions of 0.2 mcg /kg/h dexmedetomidine intravenously in group D and 50 mL 0.2 ml/kg/h normal saline intravenously in group MF. After aseptic painting and draping of the surgical field, local anaesthetic was administered 15 minutes after the start of loading doses with Inj. Lignocaine 2% with 1:200000 adrenaline.

Heart rate (HR) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) were measured at baseline, 10 minutes after the loading dosage was completed, 15 minutes after local anaesthetic infiltration, and then every 15 minutes until the procedure was completed. Sedation and analgesia were monitored every 20 minutes until the surgery was completed and titrated to RSS 3 and VAS 3 respectively. In the event of insufficient effect, midazolam 0.01 mg/kg

and Fentanyl 1g/kg intravenously were given as rescue sedation and rescue analgesia, respectively, with a maximum of four doses of rescue medications. If the intended level of sedation or analgesia was not achieved with the clinically indicated drug dose limit, another anaesthetic technique was to be initiated, and the study was to be terminated. Any negative consequences were documented. In the recovery room, every 30 minutes for 2 hours, pulse rate, MAP, duration of analgesia, and Ramsay Sedation Score (RSS) were assessed. The surgeon was directed not to deliver any analgesic agent to the patient post-operatively without first consulting with the investigator or until the patient requested analgesia.

Result

A study of 60 Patients were randomly divided in two groups of 30 each. In present study, age, gender, & ASA grade are shown in table 1.

Table 1: General Characteristics

Characteristics	Group D (n=30)	Group MF (n=30)
Age in years (Mean \pm SD)	29.8 \pm 10.4	30.1 \pm 11.25
Gender (M/F)	17/13	18/12
ASA Grade (I/II)	28/2	27/3

The mean sedation score in Group D was 3.68 \pm 0.62 and in Group MF was 3.38 \pm 0.16. p value was >0.05 and was not statistically significant. Pain scores calculated using Visual analog scale were significantly lower in Group D (0.81 \pm 0.42) compared to Group M (2.02 \pm 0.72) in the intraoperative period Table 2

Table 2: Various scores of patients of group D & Group MF

Parameter	Group D (Mean + SD)	Group MF (Mean + SD)	P Value
Sedation score	3.68 \pm 0.62	3.38 \pm 0.16	0.062
Visual analogue score	0.81 \pm 0.42	2.02 \pm 0.72	0.002

The difference in mean pulse rates between Group D and Group MF intraoperatively from 30 minute onwards to the end of surgery and postoperatively till 60 minutes was significant. (Table 3)

Table 3: Comparison of heart rate (beats per minute) in Group D and Group MF

Time	Group D (n=50)		Group MF (n=50)		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Intraoperatively					
0 min	81.72	12.86	80.3	8.55	0.622
10 min	66.45	9.23	77.52	7.54	0.643
15 min	71.4	9.12	74.54	6.82	0.066
30 min	70.42	8.84	74.42	6.23	<0.001*
45 min	68.42	7.85	73.42	6.42	<0.001*
60 min	67.32	7.84	71.18	7.45	<0.001*
75 min	63.43	6.2	72.42	6.32	<0.001*
90 min	62.23	6.43	73.43	5.86	<0.001*
105 min	66.94	6.54	73.84	6.12	<0.001*
120 min	67.72	8.53	73.42	6.43	<0.001*
Postoperatively					
0 min	67.73	7.52	73.58	7.12	<0.001*
30 min	71.42	8.32	74.62	6.57	<0.001*
60 min	73.23	7.54	76.42	6.72	0.385
90 min	75.53	7.82	77.42	6.12	0.276
120 min	76.42	8.42	78.43	5.23	0.312

Figure 1: Intraoperative comparison of Heart rate in Group D & Group MF

Figure 2: Postoperative comparison of Heart rate in Group D & Group MF

The difference in mean arterial pressures between Group D and Group MF intraoperatively from 45 minute onwards to end of surgery and postoperatively till 30 minutes was significant (Table 4)

Table 4: Comparison of mean arterial pressure (mm Hg) in Group D and Group MF

Time	Group D (n=50)		Group MF (n=50)		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Intraoperatively					
0 min	94.42	6.53	93.73	6.85	0.743
10 min	86.58	6.68	86.52	6.58	0.073
15 min	87.42	6.82	86.84	7.42	0.254
30 min	83.42	6.48	84.35	7.89	0.176
45 min	79.41	6.36	83.62	7.34	<0.001*
60 min	76.82	6.86	82.14	7.62	<0.001*
75 min	73.84	6.42	81.68	7.78	<0.001*
90 min	75.62	6.92	82.23	7.23	<0.001*
105 min	79.42	6.48	84.64	6.68	<0.001*
120 min	81.64	6.92	87.15	6.23	<0.001*
Postoperatively					
0 min	85.52	6.72	88.64	6.89	<0.001*
30 min	86.64	6.84	89.24	6.45	0.352
60 min	88.62	6.12	89.64	6.38	0.852
90 min	89.86	5.88	90.45	6.82	0.74
120 min	91.46	5.92	91.84	6.47	0.093

Figure 3: Intraoperative comparison of MAP in Group D & Group MF

Figure 4: Postoperative comparison of MAP in Group D & Group MF

Discussion

In adult patients, ENT surgery such as tympanoplasty is typically performed under local anaesthesia or local anaesthesia with sedation under monitored anaesthesia care (MAC). [14] MAC may be used for a variety of ENT procedures where appropriate sedation and analgesia without respiratory depression are desired for the comfort of both the patient and the surgeon. [15] Local anaesthetic combined with intravenous sedation has several advantages, including

decreased bleeding, cost effectiveness, postoperative analgesia, speedier patient movement, and the opportunity to assess hearing intraoperatively. [16]

Parikh *et al.* [17] compared Dexmedetomidine to Midazolam-Fentanyl sedation and determined that both medications were comparable. In their study, 1 patient in Group D and 4 patients in Group M required rescue sedation with Propofol. In

our study, the sedation score was somewhat greater in Group D than in Group M, but this difference was found to be statistically insignificant. Similar findings were observed in a study conducted by Vyas *et al.* [18], where the difference in sedation score between the two groups was found to be statistically insignificant. In our study, we observed that perioperative VAS scores in Group D were significantly lower than in Group M, indicating that Dexmedetomidine provides superior analgesia than Midazolam.

Karaaslan *et al.* [19] observed that the amount of rescue analgesia required in the Dexmedetomidine group was significantly lower than in the Midazolam group, indicating that Dexmedetomidine had a better analgesic effect. Padmaja and Varma [20] examined the efficacy of Midazolam with Dexmedetomidine in minor ENT procedures, concluding that Dexmedetomidine minimises the doses of rescue analgesics, making it a better choice for ENT surgery.

Parikh *et al.* [17] found that intraoperative mean heart rate and mean arterial pressure was lower in Dexmedetomidine group than the baseline values and the corresponding values in Midazolam-Fentanyl group. In our study also, we found significant reduction in heart rate, and Mean arterial pressure in Group D compared to baseline values and corresponding values in Group M.

Durmus *et al.* [21] evaluated this property of Dexmedetomidine for providing controlled hypotension in general anaesthesia for tympanoplasty cases and concluded that it is a useful adjuvant to decrease bleeding in cases where bloodless surgical field is required

Conclusion

Dexmedetomidine is a safer medication than midazolam with fentanyl because it provides greater sedation and perioperative analgesia with less need for rescue analgesics. Because

of its anxiolytic properties, it also normalises the elevations in blood pressure and heart rate produced by perioperative anxiety. It is inexpensive and has no negative side effects.

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